

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PECULIARITIES OF COMPUTER TESTING APPLICATION AT CLINICAL DEPARTMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the possibilities to apply computer testing as one of the most objective methods of students' assessment. The main advantages and disadvantages of this method are suggested considering the necessity to develop clinical thinking of future doctors.

Keywords: computer testing.

The purpose to control student knowledge is to correct a didactic process and assess its efficacy in general. Pedagogical supervision is a considerable part of the educational process and professional training of a medical specialist. One of the functions of pedagogical supervision is a diagnostic one enabling to determine the level of the material mastered by students. Various methods to control knowledge and skills are applied in the educational process.

There are two methods to control student knowledge: subjective and objective. The subjective method of control means detection, assessment and evaluation of knowledge, abilities and skills due to personal judgment of an examiner. This method of assessment cannot be applied for the final testing, as it does not possess the necessary accuracy and reproduction of results. The objective control is the method possessing essential accuracy and reproduction of results. The instrument enabling to assess objectively the quality of knowledge obtained is the test including a test task and a pattern according to which the quality of knowledge mastered can be evaluated. Computer testing at different stages of the educational process occupies an important position in training students and enables not only to evaluate the level of mastering the subject but also correct the process of learning [3].

The history of tests as a method to evaluate personal parameters numbers several centuries. Even antique sophists differentiating between the nature and human being suggested an idea of self-determination of the personality on the basis of individualization of training. This conception in the ethics of education of sophists was based on mechanical transmission and checking learners' believes, and expansion of the sphere of cognition use by analogy. In 1846 in Great Britain J. Fisher was the first to use the method of testing to assess the knowledge of pupils. The first pedagogical test was created by Edward Lee Thorndike in 1904, in the 20-30-s of the last century with the participation of L.S. Vygotskyi, O.M. Leontyev, L.S. Rubinshtein et al. a classical theory of tests was formed.

Professor V.S. Avanesov differentiated four forms of test tasks: an open form of test tasks, a closed form of test tasks, conformity tasks and tasks to find a correct succession [1]. The open form of test tasks requires a correct definition formulated by a person tested. It is in the form of an incomplete judgment with one element absent. Usually a person tested inserts a missing figure and (or) a word (word combination). The closed form

of test tasks requires the choice of a right option out of the suggested ones. A person tested should choose a correct answer. The tasks to find conformity suggest detection of pairs among multiple objects offered. The task consists of two groups of elements with an accurate formulation of choice criteria of conformity between them. The tasks to determine a correct succession require detection of an order of the objects suggested (figures, words, symbols). The task contains a lot of unsettled elements. A specified order should be defined between them.

Modern possibilities of information technologies enable to assess the knowledge in the form of computer testing. Application of computer programs to determine the level of students' knowledge in comparison with a classical oral questioning has a number of advantages:

- it increases technical effectiveness of the procedure of checking; ensures automatic checking, saved a teacher from the necessity to check with hands, increases objective evaluation, makes the time of checking shorter, and at last, enables to give up from paper variants of tasks and answers;
- a student has a possibility to be aware of his/her mark (or total score) immediately after computer testing;
- it enables to use program-didactic test tasks presented in different forms;
- it enables to fill in the data base and design the variants of tests for different chapters of the subject studied;
- it enables to process the results of test tasks statistically including the analysis of correctness of tasks. At the end an accurate assessment of knowledge in the subject, abilities and practical skills of every student becomes possible.

Nowadays computer testing is the first stage of both intermediate and final module tests. Test methods are considered the most objective, technological and effective, their use to check the quality of students' training at different stages of education do not provoke any doubt even among strong supporters of more traditional methods of students' evaluation. The system of test control activates the works of students during the whole term, improves relations in "teacher-student" system, and ensures deeper and stronger mastering complicated material. Stage-by-stage diagnostics of knowledge enables the teachers to correct the methods of teaching in time, and a leading task is management of cognitive activity of students and control of their results.

The quality of test tasks is of great importance for objective assessment of students. The most important requirement for tests is an adequate purpose. They should be in the form of clinical situation tasks for medical students. While compiling tests pedagogical requirements should be observed: their validity, reliability and single value. The tests should be compiled in that way to minimize the probability of their guessing by students at random. A test task should be completely seen on the display, size of the test number and color design of tasks should correspond to ergonomic requirements.

There are a number of recommendations to compile computer tests [2]. All the answers of every task should be credible making a student to analyze every variant of an answer and find incorrectness or an error in it. In the tasks where it is possible several correct answers should be given, each of them supplements other correct answers. A correct statement should not be absolutely identical with those definitions contained in the textbook to prevent immediate guess of a correct answer. With this aim incorrect answers can be given on purpose, they are consonant with definitions contained in the textbooks. The questions to every topic should be chosen in that way to include all the chapters from the course and enable to control theoretical knowledge mastered by students and skills to apply this knowledge in the practice.

However, to our mind, the value of computer testing at clinical departments should not be over-estimated. A teacher should not focus on the results of test only, since high results can be caused by formal learning of tests by the first phrases or key words. Computer testing which is much spoken about does not practically influence on the formation of clinical thinking of students – future doctors. Students should know that testing is only a part of assessment and not the principal one. At clinical departments assessment of students' knowledge should be based on the work near the patient's bed, mastering practical skills, ability to solve clinical situation tasks, interpret data of additional methods of examination etc. In addition, test tasks themselves should contain a dominant amount of questions concerning diagnostics and treatment of nervous diseases.

Computer testing contrary to other forms of testing enables to assess knowledge quickly and objectively, which is rather important in the organization of educational process, determine the volume of essential information considering individual training of one students and the whole group. Although, effective application of computer testing is possible only in case the group is supplied with computers one hundred per cent. In other case only irrational use of working time can be

stated. Computer testing regularly stimulates students to systematic training with a wider use of educational literature, promotes their quick orientation in a certain subject, and improves thinking processes. It should be noted that existing tests corresponds to the first level of knowledge that restricts their wide use. Moreover, as a rule, test tasks have only one right option (multiple choice tasks). Test tasks containing 3 right options out of 5 suggested can be more effective, and the value of each should be considered. The issue concerning the data base available for students is a disputable one. In this case a student is able to prepare for testing purposefully, get a positive result, although there is no appropriate general training on a certain topic.

A problematic issue is insufficient amount of questions of the III level of knowledge to determine clinical thinking of a student, ability to make diagnostic and therapeutic-tactic algorithm. The principal task of training students at higher educational medical establishments is formation of clinical thinking directed to diagnostics of a disease and application of modern therapeutic tactics. Insufficiency of interactive programs should be stated here which is rather important not for controlling but for training in case patients are not available.

Therefore, test tasks are an effective educational stimulus promoting application of the acquired theoretical skills for solution of clinical tasks. Clearly set time limits activate thinking activity of students and teach them to solve a task quickly. Evaluation criteria accurately determined enable to assess the level of the program material mastered by students objectively. Computer testing makes it possible to test a big number of students at one time. Due to computer testing a teacher is able to control the level of knowledge mastered in all the educational material or in one certain topic. To our mind, testing in learning clinical subjects, and neurology in particular, is only an additional method to assess the students' knowledge.

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